

Reducing PD-1/PD-L1 connections by inducing spinor quantum noise waves in exchanged information between hemoglobin, T-cells and tumor cells through bird stem cells-a hypothesis

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Abstract: Up to date, it has been known that tumor cells response to attacks of T-cells by producing some PD-1/PD-L1 connections. Unfortunately, medical methods for preventing of these connections are very expensive and sometimes non-effective. We suggest a new way for reducing these connections by producing some noises in exchanged information between tumor cells, T-cells and controller cells like heart ones. In this model, we assume that human cells use of spinor waves for exchanging information. Because, the velocity of exchanged information between two spinors which are located in a large distant is more than the velocity of light. In fact, two spinors could send and receive information from another spinor immediately. In this hypothesis, DNAs within heart cells or any controller are built from some spinors like electrons and by their motions, some waves are emerged. These spinor waves are taken by iron atoms and multigonal molecules within hemoglobins and other spinors within blood vessels. Hemoglobins are located on some blood cells, move along blood vessels and give their information into cells, proteins and RNAs. Spinors within hemoglobins and ions within blood vessels are entanglement and could transmit any information between cells. Thus, when a tumor is emerged, its spinor waves are changed and transmitted very fast into heart cells. Heart cells diagnose these quantum waves and by using entanglement between spinors within blood vessels and hemoglobins, send some messages to T-cells. These messages are taken by tumor cells and they become ready to response to attacks. To prevent of receiving information by tumor cells, we can use of some extra cells or hemoglobins which interact with spinors and hemoglobins around tumor cells and produce some noises. We have done some experiments on embryonic stem cells and blood ones and find that they could build some biological wires. We suggest that these wires could be used in producing noises and transferring information from a receiver to tumor cells. Science quantum spinor waves are very small and have very minor power and intensity, we couldn't detect them by present electronic device and for this reason, we suggest for using biological cells.

Keywords: Tumor cells, Hemoglobin, Quantum, Spinor, T-cells

I.Introduction:

One of main problems in cancer diseases is preventing of connections between programmed cell death protein (PD-1) on a T-cell and the programmed death-ligand 1 (PD-L1) on the tumor cells. Interactions between these cell surface proteins are involved in the suppression of the immune system and limit the killing of tumor cells by T-cells [1]. Thus, use of an inhibitor that blocks the interaction between PD-L1 and the PD-1 receptor can prevent the cancer from evading the immune system [2]. Up to date, many PD-1/PD-L1 inhibitors had been approved which could be used for the treatment of different forms of cancers like melanoma, non-small cell lung cancer, renal cell carcinoma, bladder cancer and Hodgkin lymphoma [3,4]. Up to date, many discussions and investigations have been done on this problem. For example, some authors have summarized and discussed the current understanding of mechanisms promoting resistance to anti-PD1/PDL1 therapies, and how combination strategies which target these pathways might yield better outcomes for patients [5]. Another investigation has shown that the approved checkpoint inhibitors (PD1 and PDL1 inhibitors) have similar efficacy and safety profiles for some cancers like bladder cancer, but they vary in dose and frequency and cost burden. However, only pembrolizumab has shown superiority over standard chemotherapy in a randomized Phase III setting [6]. Another authors have disclosed that most of the patients can not benefit from anti-PD1/PDL1 therapy. Furthermore, a large group of responders would develop acquired resistance after initial responses. To break these resistances and improve anti-PD1/PDL1 methods, they have considered the strategies that may relieve the anti-PD1/PDL1 resistance [7]. Another study has shown that the expression of PD-L1 is highly prevalent in some cancers like prostate cancer. PD-L1 is closely related to Gleason score and may be a co-factor associated with the progression of prostate cancer [8]. Another research has suggested that PD1/PDL1 expression and immune response varied at different microsatellite statuses in some cancers like gastric cancer. PD1/PDL1 expression was correlated with CD8+ T cell/CD68+ M densities in this cancer at different microsatellite statuses, especially at the invasion front [9]. Another article has indicated that combined treatment of expanded natural killer (NK) cells and PD1-blockade resulted in robust synergistic tumor destruction of initially non-responding patient tumors. Thus, expanded NK cells may overcome the critical roadblocks to extending the prodigious benefits of PD1-blockade therapy to more patients with lung cancer and other tumor types [10].

Most of these considerations show that some of present drugs and treatments for PD-1/PD-L1 connections are expensive and may be non-helpful or effective. Now, the question arises that is there any probability that electromagnetic waves act as effective PD-1/PD-L1 inhibitors. Recently, some scientists are using of electromagnetic waves to cure cancers. For example, current experimental evidence suggests that tumor-specific modulation frequencies regulate the expression of genes involved in migration and invasion and disrupt the mitotic spindle. This novel targeted treatment approach is emerging as an appealing therapeutic option for patients with advanced cancer given its excellent tolerability [11]. Some authors have reviewed the experimental and clinical evidence of pulsed electromagnetic field (PEMF) therapy discussing future perspectives in its use in oncology [12]. Another authors have argued that specific ranges of extremely low frequency electromagnetic waves inhibits cancer cell proliferation. Their thermodynamic model selects the frequency of ELF-EMF specific for each cancer [13]. Some investigators have shown that extremely low frequency variable electromagnetic fields affect cancer and noncancerous cells in vitro differently[14]. Another paper has discussed that cancerous tissues have natural frequencies different from natural frequencies of normal tissues, and thus, one can hypothesize to irradiate cancerous tissues using EMFs at natural frequencies of cancer cells, causing resonant interaction with cellular membrane channels, inducing increasing of ions' flux across cellular channels and damaging the cellular functions of cancer cells [15]. Another work has shown that extremely low-frequency electromagnetic field altered PPAR γ and CCL2 levels and suppressed CD44⁺/CD24⁻ Breast Cancer Cells Characteristics [16]. These researches and many other investigations show that electromagnetic waves could act as the strong tool in curing cancers.

Maybe, one ask that why electromagnetic waves have these effects on cells? To answer, it should be reminded that the heart as the origin of life emit both types of electrical and magnetic waves. Up today, many models have been proposed to consider the origin of heart waves and most of them focused on the action potentials on the cell membranes or between cells [17,18]. However, it seems that there is a direct relation between these

potentials and DNA waves [19,20]. In this paper, we will consider these relations in details and propose a model for controlling cancer cells and reducing PD-1/PD-L1 connections by using electromagnetic waves.

II. Theoretical method

II-A: The role of hemoglobin in exchanging information between heart and cells and reducing PD-1/PD-L1 connections:

Up to date, it has been known that hemoglobins play the main role in exchanging oxygen with cells. However, these molecules include iron atoms which could attract magnetic wave and induce some quantum waves into multi-gonal molecules. Thus, we could suppose that these molecules could store some waves in some places and then give them to other molecules in other places. Now, the question arises that how these molecules store information?

The best quantum method for storing information is using of spinor waves. Spinors are particles like electrons with spins= $1/2, 3/2, \dots$. These particles obey of Pauli repulsive principle. This means that two parallel spins repel each other and two anti-parallel spins attract each other. The velocity of exchanging information between two spins is more than velocity of light (Please see figure 1). For example, in a pair of two spins, when the arrow of one spin changes, the arrow of another spin change very fast. This entanglement between two spinors could be affected by adding some extra spinors. For example, an extra spinor produces new entanglement with one of two entangled spinors and decreases previous entanglement (See Figure 2). Now, how these concepts could help us to consider the methods for storing information in hemoglobins?

To answer this question, first, we return to DNAs within cells, specially heart cells, and more specially, those cells which produce electromagnetic waves. Mostly, scientists assume that the origin of these waves are some action potentials. However, the question arises that what is the origin of these potentials. We could go a step more and deep into heart cells. Suppose that a DNA is built from charged particles and by its motions, some waves are emerged. These waves are produced by vibrations of spinors like electrons within cells and could be absorbed by spinors out of cells. These waves could be divided into two parts:

1. Some quantum waves produce observed magnetic and electrical waves and cause to action potential of heart.
2. Some quantum waves could be absorbed by spinors like electrons or iron atoms within the hemoglobin or even by multigonal molecules of hemoglobin (See figure 3).

Heart thus could do two affairs:

1. Heart cells could produce some waves and force into blood cells for moving along vessels.
2. Heart cells could induce spinor waves into hemoglobins and store information within them (See figure 4).

Hemoglobin could be located within blood cells, move along vessels and reach to special cells. Then, hemoglobin could induce its information as spinor waves into hexagonal/pentagonal molecules of a DNA (See Figure 5) or within the coil-like structures of some proteins (See Figure 6).

Maybe, one ask that how we could use of this mechanism in curing cancers? To response to this question, we should remember that blood includes many ions and spinors. Thus, a heart could induce any new information into all spinors within blood vessels and change information which is stored in a hemoglobin. For example, when a tumor is emerged, its changes has a direct effect on spinor waves and these waves and information are received by heart cells immediately. Then, heart cells send new information to all cells and special T-cells for making best conditions in curing and attacking to tumors. Unfortunately, these information are taken by tumor cells and they become ready to response to any attack. For example, they produce some PD-1/PD-L1 connections and kill T-cells (See Figure 7).

Now, one could ask how we could prevent of receiving information by tumor cells? To answer this question, we suggest several ways:

1. We could use of some extra harmless cells which interact with hemoglobins around tumor cells and produce some noises in received information by tumor (See Figure 8).
2. We can use of some extra hemoglobins which interact with hemoglobins around tumor cells and produce noises in main waves (See Figure 9).

In below, we bring some calculations which show that by increasing numbers of molecules or cells include spinors, we can break the entanglement between heart

spinors and hemoglobins around tumor cells (See figure 10). Consequently, tumor cells don't notice the new messages exchanged between other parts of body and don't wait any attack of T-cells and they can kill cancer cells. In fact, figure 10 shows the needed spinors which produce some noises around tumor cells and reduce the probability for producing PD1/PD-L1 connections.

II-B: Mathematical model:

$$|Two\ Spin\ function\rangle = F\{ \mathcal{N} \sum_i [1 + |Two\ quantum\ spinors, i\rangle] \otimes \sum_j [1 + |Two\ quantum\ spin, j\rangle]\}$$

$$|Two\ quantum\ spinors, i\rangle = \cos\alpha \sum_{n=0,1} \tan^n \alpha |\uparrow, n\rangle_{+1} |\downarrow, n\rangle_{-1}$$

$$\tan\alpha \approx \exp\left(-\frac{\pi E_{spinor}}{T_{spinor}}\right)$$

$$|Two\ quantum\ spin, j\rangle = \frac{1}{\cosh\alpha} \sum_{m=0,\infty} \tanh^m \alpha |\uparrow\uparrow, m\rangle_{+1} |\downarrow\downarrow, m\rangle_{-1}$$

$$\tanh\alpha \approx \exp\left(-\frac{\pi E_{spin}}{T_{spin}}\right)$$

$$\text{Correlation function} = \langle Two\ Spin\ function | Two\ Spin\ function \rangle = 1$$

$$F^2\{ \mathcal{N} \sum_i [1 + |two\ quantum\ spinors, i\rangle] \otimes \sum_j [1 + |two\ quantum\ spin, j\rangle]\} = 1$$

$$|\uparrow, 0\rangle = \cos\beta \sum_{l=0,1} \tan^l \beta |\uparrow, l\rangle_{+1} |\downarrow, l\rangle_{-1}$$

$$|\uparrow\uparrow, 0\rangle = \frac{1}{\cosh\beta} \sum_{k=0,\infty} \tanh^k \beta |\uparrow\uparrow, k\rangle_{+1} |\downarrow\downarrow, k\rangle_{-1}$$

$$| \text{three quantum spinors}, i \rangle =$$

$$\cos\alpha \cos\beta \cos\beta' \sum_{l=0,1} \sum_{n=0,1} \tan^n \alpha \tan^l \beta \tan^{l'} \beta'$$

$$| [|\uparrow, l\rangle_{+1} |\downarrow, l\rangle_{-1}], n\rangle_{+1} | [|\downarrow, l'\rangle_{+1} |\uparrow, l'\rangle_{-1}], n\rangle_{-1}$$

$$| \text{three quantum spins}, j \rangle =$$

$$\frac{1}{\cosh\alpha \cosh\beta \cosh\beta'} \sum_{k,k'=0,\infty} \sum_{n=0,\infty} \tanh^n \alpha \tanh^k \beta \tanh^{k'} \beta'$$

$$| [|\uparrow\uparrow, k\rangle_{+1} |\downarrow\downarrow, k\rangle_{-1}], n\rangle_{+1} | [|\downarrow\downarrow, k'\rangle_{+1} |\uparrow\uparrow, k'\rangle_{-1}], n\rangle_{-1}$$

$$| N - \text{quantum spinors}, i \rangle =$$

$$\cos\alpha_1 \dots \cos\alpha_N \sum_{l_1=0,1} \dots \sum_{l_N=0,1} \tan^{l_1} \alpha_1 \dots \tan^{l_N} \alpha_N$$

$$| [|\uparrow, l_1\rangle_{+1} |\downarrow, l_1\rangle_{-1}], \dots, [|\uparrow, l_N\rangle_{+1} |\downarrow, l_N\rangle_{-1}], N\rangle_{+1} \otimes |$$

$$| [|\downarrow, l_1\rangle_{+1} |\uparrow, l_1\rangle_{-1}], \dots, [|\downarrow, l_N\rangle_{+1} |\uparrow, l_N\rangle_{-1}], N\rangle_{+1} |$$

$$| N - \text{quantum spins}, j \rangle =$$

$$\frac{1}{\cosh\alpha \dots \cosh\alpha_N} \sum_{m_1=0,\infty} \dots \sum_{m_N=0,\infty} \tan^{m_1} \alpha_1 \dots \tan^{m_N} \alpha_N$$

$$| [|\uparrow\uparrow, m_1\rangle_{+1} |\downarrow\downarrow, m_1\rangle_{-1}], \dots, [|\uparrow\uparrow, m_N\rangle_{+1} |\downarrow\downarrow, m_N\rangle_{-1}], N\rangle_{+1} \otimes |$$

$$| [|\downarrow\downarrow, m_1\rangle_{+1} |\uparrow\uparrow, m_1\rangle_{-1}], \dots, [|\downarrow\downarrow, m_N\rangle_{+1} |\uparrow\uparrow, m_N\rangle_{-1}], N\rangle_{+1} |$$

$$| \text{Entangled } N - \text{quantum spinors and spins}, i \rangle =$$

$$\cos\alpha_1 \dots \cos\alpha_N \sum_{l_1=0,1} \dots \sum_{l_N=0,1} \tan^{l_1} \alpha_1 \dots \tan^{l_N} \alpha_N \otimes$$

$$\frac{1}{\cosh\alpha \dots \cosh\alpha_N} \sum_{m_1=0,\infty} \dots \sum_{m_N=0,\infty} \tan^{m_1} \alpha_1 \dots \tan^{m_N} \alpha_N \otimes$$

$$|[\uparrow, \uparrow, l_1\rangle_{+1} | \downarrow, \downarrow, l_1\rangle_{-1}], \dots [|\uparrow, \uparrow, l_N\rangle_{+1} | \downarrow, \downarrow, l_N\rangle_{-1}], N\rangle_{+1} \otimes |$$

$$|[\downarrow, \downarrow, l_1\rangle_{+1} | \uparrow, \uparrow, l_1\rangle_{-1}], \dots [|\downarrow, \downarrow, l_N\rangle_{+1} | \uparrow, \uparrow, l_N\rangle_{-1}], N\rangle_{+1} |$$

$$|Total\ function\rangle =$$

$$G\{ \mathcal{N}$$

$$\otimes \Sigma_n [1 + | N - quantum\ spinors , i, i, m, n\rangle]$$

$$\otimes \Sigma_m [1 + | N - quantum\ spins , i, i, m, n\rangle]$$

$$\otimes \Sigma_i [1 + | Entangled\ N - quantum\ spinors\ and\ spins , i, i, m, n\rangle]$$

$$\otimes \Sigma_j [1 + | Entangled\ N - quantum\ spinors\ and\ spins , i, j, m, n\rangle]]\}$$

$$1 \gggg G\{ \mathcal{N}$$

$$\otimes \Sigma_n [1 + | N - quantum\ spinors , i, i, m, n\rangle]$$

$$\otimes \Sigma_m [1 + | N - quantum\ spins , i, i, m, n\rangle]$$

$$\otimes \Sigma_i [1 + | Entangled\ N - quantum\ spinors\ and\ spins , i, i, m, n\rangle]$$

$$\otimes \Sigma_j [1 + | Entangled\ N - quantum\ spinors\ and\ spins , i, j, m, n\rangle]]\}$$

$$\otimes G^*\{ \mathcal{N}$$

$$\otimes \Sigma_n [1 + | N - quantum\ spinors , i, i, m, n\rangle]$$

$$\otimes \Sigma_m [1 + | N - quantum\ spins , i, i, m, n\rangle]$$

$$\otimes \Sigma_i [1 + | Entangled\ N - quantum\ spinors\ and\ spins , i, i, m, n\rangle]$$

$$\otimes \Sigma_j [1 + | Entangled\ N - quantum\ spinors\ and\ spins , i, j, m, n\rangle]]\}$$

Fig 1: Two spinors exchange information with velocity faster than light

Fig2: An extra spinors decreases entanglement between two spinors

Fig 3: The process of formation of different frequencies of electrical and magnetic fields and their related spinors by heart

Induction of information (spinor waves) into multigonal molecules of hemoglobin by heart

Fig 4: Induction of information (spinor waves) into multigonal molecules of hemoglobin by heart

Fig 5: Induction of information into DNA bases by hemoglobins

Induction of information
within biological structures
like proteins by hemoglobins

Fig 6: Induction of information within biological structures like proteins by hemoglobins

Fig 7: Both T-cells and tumor cells take sended information by heart

Fig 8: Extra cells could induce noises into hemoglobin

Interactions between spins of hemoglobins cause to information lost

Fig 9: A new hemoglobin may induce new information into previous hemoglobin

Fig 10: Correlation function between spinors in hemoglobins in terms of number of spins

III. Experimental Results

To produce noise around tumor cells, we suggest using of stem cell wires or blood cell wires. To this aim, we did some experiments on the bird egg cells and bring results in below:

A: Bird stem cells are very active and approximately harmless for human. Thus, we could use of these cells for inducing noises around tumor cells. These noises cause that tumor cells become non-aware from attacks of T-cells and don't produce related toxins and proteins to response.

1. Usually, bird embryonic stem cells are confined within a boundary. However, under a pressure, this boundary could be broken and cells become active (See Figure 11).
2. Bird embryonic cells are so active that seem to interact with microbes or even themselves act like some microbes (Figure 12).
3. Bird embryonic cells or stem cells in initial stages could produce some biological wires. These wires could be sent into human's body through mouth and reach to tumor cells (See Figure 13-15).
4. Stem cells could interact with other cells. Figures 16-18 show that these cells may act like some microbes and attack to some cells. Thus, we can hope that these cells interact with blood cells around tumor and make some noises in exchanging information between hemoglobins and tumor cells.

B: Bird blood cells have hemoglobin and could join to each other and form some biological wires (See figures 19-23). These wires are usually harmless for human and could be entered into human's body through mouth and reach to tumor cells. Then, iron atoms within these wires could take information from a receiver and transmit it to tumor cells.

Fig 11: Stem cells within their boundaries in an egg

Fig 12: Interactions between stem cells and microbes

Fig 13: Stem cells could join to each other and form a biological wire (First picture)

Fig 14: Stem cells could join to each other and form a biological wire (Second picture)

Fig 15: Stem cells could join to each other and form a biological wire (Third picture)

Fig 16: Stem cells could act like a microbe and interact with cells (First picture)

Fig 17: Stem cells could act like a microbe and interact with cells (Second picture)

Fig 18: Stem cells could act like a microbe and interact with cells (Third picture)

Fig 19: Blood cells join to each other and form a biological wire (First picture)

Fig20: Blood cells join to each other and form a biological wire (Second picture)

Fig 21: Blood cells join to each other and form a biological wire (Third picture)

Fig 22: Blood cells join to each other and form a biological wire (Forth picture)

Fig 23: Blood cells join to each other and form a biological wire (Fifth picture)

Conclusions:

A DNA is built from hexagonal/pentagonal bases and many electrons. Consequently, by its motions, some spinor waves are emerged. These waves are taken by spinors out of cells and produce some entanglement between them. For example, DNA waves within heart cells are taken by iron atoms and multigonal molecules within hemoglobins and also some other spinors within blood vessels. These molecules move along vessels and give their information into cells, proteins and RNAs. The velocity of transferring information between spinors is very faster than velocity of light . Thus, when a tumor is emerged, heart cells understand very fast and send some messages to T-cells. These messages are taken by tumor cells and make them ready to response. By inducing some noises, one can prevent of receiving information by tumor cells. To this aim, bird stem cells and their blood ones could be suggested.

References:

- [1] Alsaab HO, Sau S, Alzhrani R, Tatiparti K, Bhise K, Kashaw SK, Iyer AK (23 August 2017). "PD-1 and PD-L1 Checkpoint Signaling Inhibition for Cancer Immunotherapy: Mechanism, Combinations, and Clinical Outcome". *Frontiers in Pharmacology*. **8**: 561. doi:10.3389/fphar.2017.00561. PMC 5572324. PMID 28878676.
- [2] Syn NL, Teng MW, Mok TS, Soo RA (December 2017). "De-novo and acquired resistance to immune checkpoint targeting". *The Lancet. Oncology*. **18** (12): e731–e741. doi:10.1016/s1470-2045(17)30607-1. PMID 29208439.
- [3] Sunshine J, Taube JM (August 2015). "PD-1/PD-L1 inhibitors". *Current Opinion in Pharmacology*. **23**: 32–8. doi:10.1016/j.coph.2015.05.011. PMC 4516625.
- [4] Gong J, Chehrazi-Raffle A, Reddi S, Salgia R (January 2018). "Development of PD-1 and PD-L1 inhibitors as a form of cancer immunotherapy: a comprehensive review of registration trials and future considerations". *Journal for Immunotherapy of Cancer*. **6** (1): 8. doi:10.1186/s40425-018-0316-z .
- [5] Jake S. O'Donnell, Georgina V. Long, Richard A. Scolyer, Michele W.L. Teng, Mark J. Smyth, Resistance to PD1/PDL1 checkpoint inhibition, *Cancer Treatment Reviews*, Volume 52, 2017, Pages 71-81, ISSN 0305-7372, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ctrv.2016.11.007>.

- [6] David D Stenehjem, Dao Tran, Michael A Nkrumah, and Shilpa Gupta, PD1/PDL1 inhibitors for the treatment of advanced urothelial bladder cancer, *Onco Targets Ther.* 2018; 11: 5973–5989.
- [7] Lei Q, Wang D, Sun K, Wang L, Zhang Y. Resistance Mechanisms of Anti-PD1/PDL1 Therapy in Solid Tumors. *Front Cell Dev Biol.* 2020;8:672. Published 2020 Jul 21. doi:10.3389/fcell.2020.00672.
- [8] He, J., Yi, M., Tan, L. *et al.* The immune checkpoint regulator PD-L1 expression are associated with clinical progression in prostate cancer. *World J Surg Onc* 19, 215 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12957-021-02325-z>
- [9] Wang YL, Gong Y, Lv Z, Li L, Yuan Y. Expression of PD1/PDL1 in gastric cancer at different microsatellite status and its correlation with infiltrating immune cells in the tumor microenvironment. *J Cancer.* 2021;12(6):1698-1707. Published 2021 Jan 18. doi:10.7150/jca.40500.
- [10] Poznanski SM, Ritchie TM, Fan IY, et al. Expanded human NK cells from lung cancer patients sensitize patients' PDL1-negative tumors to PD1-blockade therapy. *J Immunother Cancer.* 2021;9(1):e001933. doi:10.1136/jitc-2020-001933.
- [11] Zimmerman JW, Jimenez H, Pennison MJ, et al. Targeted treatment of cancer with radiofrequency electromagnetic fields amplitude-modulated at tumor-specific frequencies. *Chin J Cancer.* 2013;32(11):573-581. doi:10.5732/cjc.013.10177.
- [12] Vadalà M, Morales-Medina JC, Vallelunga A, Palmieri B, Laurino C, Iannitti T. Mechanisms and therapeutic effectiveness of pulsed electromagnetic field therapy in oncology. *Cancer Med.* 2016;5(11):3128-3139. doi:10.1002/cam4.861
- [13] Loredana Bergandi, Umberto Lucia, Giulia Grisolia, Riccarda Granata, Iacopo Gesmundo, Antonio Ponzetto, Emilio Paolucci, Romano Borchiellini, Ezio Ghigo, Francesca Silvagno, The extremely low frequency electromagnetic stimulation selective for cancer cells elicits growth arrest through a metabolic shift, *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) - Molecular Cell Research*, Volume 1866, Issue 9, 2019, Pages 1389-1397, ISSN 0167-4889, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbamcr.2019.05.006>.
- [14] Anna Koziorowska, Maria Romerowicz-Misielak, Przemysław Sołek & Marek Koziorowski (2018) Extremely low frequency variable electromagnetic fields affect cancer and noncancerous cells *in vitro* differently: Preliminary study, *Electromagnetic Biology and Medicine*, 37:1, 35-42, DOI: [10.1080/15368378.2017.1408021](https://doi.org/10.1080/15368378.2017.1408021).

[15]_Emanuele Calabrò & Salvatore Magazù (2018) Resonant interaction between electromagnetic fields and proteins: A possible starting point for the treatment of cancer, *Electromagnetic Biology and Medicine*, 37:3, 155-168, DOI: [10.1080/15368378.2018.1499031](https://doi.org/10.1080/15368378.2018.1499031).

[16] Oh, I.-R., Raymundo, B., Jung, S.A., Kim, H.J., Park, J.-K. and Kim, C.-W. (2020), Extremely Low-Frequency Electromagnetic Field Altered PPAR γ and CCL2 Levels and Suppressed CD44⁺/CD24⁻ Breast Cancer Cells Characteristics. *Bull. Korean Chem. Soc.*, 41: 812-823. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bkcs.12072>.

[17] Hopfenfeld B, Ashikaga H. Origin of the electrocardiographic U wave: effects of M cells and dynamic gap junction coupling. *Ann Biomed Eng.* 2010;38(3):1060-1070. doi:10.1007/s10439-010-9941-5

[18] Izu LT, Xie Y, Sato D, Bányász T, Chen-Izu Y. Ca²⁺ waves in the heart. *J Mol Cell Cardiol.* 2013;58:118-124. doi:10.1016/j.yjmcc.2012.11.014.

[19] Montagnier, Luc; Aïssa, Jamal; Lavallée, Claude; Mbamy, Mireille; Varon, Joseph; Chenal, Henri (2009). "Electromagnetic detection of HIV DNA in the blood of AIDS patients treated by antiretroviral therapy". *Interdisciplinary Sciences: Computational Life Sciences*. **1** (4): 245–253. doi:10.1007/s12539-009-0059-0.

[20] *Montagnier, Luc; Del Giudice, Emilio; Aïssa, Jamal; Lavallee, Claude; Motschwiller, Steven; Capolupo, Antonio; Polcari, Albino; Romano, Paola; Tedeschi, Alberto; Vitiello, Giuseppe* (2015). "Transduction of DNA information through water and electromagnetic waves". *Electromagnetic Biology and Medicine*. **34** (2): 106–112. *arXiv:1501.01620*. doi:10.3109/15368378.2015.1036072